

KINDERGARTEN TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL CAPABILITIES DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Kindergarten Teachers' Instructional Capabilities During COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

The study delved into the level of capabilities of Kindergarten teachers in the Municipality of Pozorrubio, Pangasinan. The study determined the profile of the respondents, the level of Kindergarten instructional capabilities during a pandemic, the significant difference between the profile of the respondents and the level of kindergarten instructional qualifications during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the level of significance of the relationship and the profile variables of the respondents and the level of kindergarten instructional capabilities during COVID 19 pandemic. The descriptive method of research was used in this study. Findings showed that most of the respondents are female, in the early adulthood stage, and married; most of the respondents earned units in graduate school and enough training to teach during the COVID-19 pandemic. The level of kindergarten instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic is Highly Capable. This study concludes that Kindergarten teachers are not significantly comparable in the performance of their instructional capabilities at certain times and at certain functions. Still, there are times and cases when they are, on the other hand, comparable, and the Kindergarten teacher's level of instructional capabilities is dependent upon or affected or caused by age, highest educational attainment, and the number of relevant training in the division levels. The study recommended that Kindergarten teachers should take the initiative to pursue the highest academic degree, which is the graduate studies and doctoral degree, and should undergo professional upgrading through higher levels of training and seminar workshops; teachers should formulate a suitable plan and continue to implement sound strategies to meet the demand for new standard education, teachers and parents must have a collaborative effort in keeping track of learner's everyday activities and give strategic intervention to monitor learners' progress, and stakeholders may work with the teachers in addressing the issues and concerns they face as they shift to the new standard teaching practices. In addition, a similar study should be conducted, taking into consideration other factors and more appropriate and relevant variables to better determine the level of instructional capabilities of Kindergarten teachers.

Keywords: *kindergarten, instruction, teachers capabilities, acknowledgement*

Introduction

Education plays an essential role in shaping the lives of students. The COVID-19 crisis has obliged most education systems to adopt face-to-face teaching and learning alternatives. Many education systems moved activities online to allow instruction to continue despite school closures (OECD, 2020). The shift of the teaching-learning delivery in schools to modular distance learning made it more challenging for school personnel to deliver primary quality education. That is why DepEd leaders are constantly finding avenues to solve the problems and capacitating their teachers and school heads to become more effective in modular distance learning (Bagood, 2020).

This study will determine the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic. Instructional capabilities mean how the teachers apply their instructional delivery using different methods and strategies to deliver the lessons to the learners, how teachers assess the learning outcomes, and teachers report and give feedback on student outputs and performance, which is different from the traditional face-to-face classroom setting.

Bagood (2020) also added that identified teaching personnel and the Education Program Supervisors prepared modules starting in May 2020 in all subjects for all grade/year levels across four quarters following the "Most Essential Learning Competencies." These self-learning modules are already considered learning packages containing pre-test, discussions, and a series of evaluations/assessments. Indeed, this kind of instructional modality has been followed by public school teachers all over the Philippines. Teachers play a vital role in continuously delivering quality education amid the pandemic.

In response to this crisis and to ensure the continuity of learning while assuring the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and other employees, the Department of Education instituted DepEd Order No.12 series of 2020 to establish new learning delivery modalities in all levels embodied in the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) for the school year 2020-2021. DepEd Order No. 12 states that the COVID-19 pandemic challenges various sectors, especially in responding to fundamental rights. With physical distancing and community quarantine being among the measures to contain COVID-19, primary education is among the sectors heavily affected as schools and community learning centers are closed for the physical conduct of classes.

The Department of Education (DepEd) ensures the continuity of learning amidst the COVID-19 pandemic through Modular Distance Learning (MDL). Learners use Self-Learning Modules (SLM) based on the Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) provided by the Department of Education.

This learning modality is currently used by all public schools because, according to a survey conducted by DepEd, 8.8 million parents preferred Modular Distance Learning.

Learning through printed modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method for parents with children enrolled this academic year. This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning.

To provide clear guidance to all offices, units, schools, and community learning centers (CLCs) of the Department of Education (DepEd), learners and their parents, guardians, and stakeholders, the Department developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), a package of education interventions that will respond to fundamental education challenges brought about by COVID-19. In developing the BE-LCP, DepEd engaged internal and external stakeholders for inputs in designing a learning delivery strategy and operational direction that ensures the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and personnel of the Department.

The alternative modes of delivering learning were envisioned to reach all learners regardless of who and where they are. The Department of Education (DepEd) conducted Learning Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF) on school opening (Department of Education, 2020); it was found that Modular learning, a form of distance learning that uses Self-Learning Modules (SLM), is one of the highly convenient for most of the typical Filipino students. The SLM is based on the essential learning competencies (MELCS) the Department of Education provides. It is the backbone of the Department of Education's distance learning program, as access to technology remains a problem for most students. All public elementary schools adopted Modular Distance Learning Modality using printed instructional materials. Problems, issues, and challenges arise since institutions have to establish the quality of learning.

In the Philippines, this learning modality is currently used by all public schools because, according to a survey conducted by the Department of Education (DepEd), learning through printed and digital modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method for parents with children enrolled this academic year. This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning. The learners may ask for assistance from the teacher via email, telephone, or text instant messaging, among others. Where possible, the teacher shall visit learners needing remediation or assistance. Printed Modules will be delivered to students, parents, or guardians by the teachers or through Local Government Officials. Parents play a vital role as home facilitators. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students. Students engage themselves in learning the concepts presented in the module.

Teaching is possible but has issues and concerns due to these abrupt changes in the new educational system. The fundamental purpose of this research is to find out the teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic in the public schools in Pozorrubio Districts, Pangasinan Division II, for SY; 2021 - 2022.

Research Questions

This study determined Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic in Pangasinan Division II for the school year 2021 – 2022. Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. What are the profile variables of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. number of years teaching Kindergarten; and
 - 1.6. the number of relevant training attended?
2. What is the level of Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic in Pangasinan Division II along:
 - 2.1. preparation of self-learning modules;
 - 2.2. distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules;
 - 2.3. monitoring of students learning;
 - 2.4. assessment of learning outcomes; and
 - 2.5. reporting/feedback of student's outputs and performances?
3. Are there significant differences in Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the pandemic across their profile variables?
4. Are there significant relationships between the level of Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the pandemic and their profile variables?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive research method, which is concerned with the description of data and characteristics of a population. The goal was to acquire factual, accurate, and systematic data that can be used in averages, frequencies, and similar statistical

calculations to answer the problems in this study.

The researcher employed this research method to gain more realistic and valid information regarding the instructional qualifications of kindergarten teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. The descriptive survey method is a method that surveys, describes, and interprets what is; and reveals a condition of relationship that exists or does not exist, practices that prevail or do not prevail, and beliefs or points of view. It also refers to the characteristics, status, or practices of individuals or a particular group, Calmorin (1995).

Participants

The subjects of this study are the Kindergarten teachers in the Municipality of Pozorrubio, Pangasinan Division II, for the SY; 2021 – 2022. All kindergarten teachers in the Municipality of Pozorrubio of Pangasinan Division II are respondents to this study. The school heads are also respondents in this study to countercheck the responses of the Kindergarten teachers. There are 38 school head respondents in this study.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>District</i>	<i>Number of Kindergarten Teachers</i>	<i>Number of School Heads</i>
Pozorrubio I	22	21
Pozorrubio II	18	17
Total	40	38

Instruments

The researcher used a questionnaire checklist instrument made explicitly for the study based and adapted from DepEd Order Learning Delivery Modalities for School Year 2020 – 2021, DepED Order on the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning, DepEd Order on Suggested Strategies in the Implementation of Distance Learning Modalities, how teachers deliver their lessons, assess the learning outcomes of the learners and reporting/feedback of students outputs and performances, the constructed problems, writer’s experiences and observations as a teacher and reinforced by readings, informal interviews, and conversations of people.

Her adviser and other experts evaluated the questionnaire checklist, the Kindergarten Program Supervisor, School Principals, and Supervisors. The suggestions were incorporated in the final draft. The questionnaires were finalized after their approval by the examination committee.

The main objective of the validation is to ascertain that every question is clearly understood and within the experience of the actual respondents of the study. The questionnaire was validated by a Master teacher, Principal, and Program Supervisor. This will ensure that the respondents can answer the questionnaire and that the data to be gathered will be valid and reliable.

Procedure

Before administering the research instrument, permission was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of Pangasinan Division II and the School Heads. The researcher personally distributed and administered the questionnaires to all Kindergarten teachers in the Municipality of Pozorrubio, Pangasinan Division II. But due to the current situation, the researcher also used social media like e-mail; and Messenger to administer the survey.

Likewise, the researcher personally retrieved the same questionnaires or through social media. The researcher will keep the responses and data obtained confidential to ensure the highest degree of objectivity of reactions. The respective Kindergarten teachers of the institutions were informed and oriented by the researchers regarding the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to answer the specific problems of the study.

To determine the profile of the Kindergarten teachers, namely, age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years teaching Kindergarten, and number of relevant training and seminars attended, frequency counts and percentages were used.

The weighted mean was used to determine the level of kindergarten teachers’ instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic. The responses were categorized into five-point scales with corresponding numerical categories. The choices are classified as “Highly Capable,” “Capable,” “Moderately Capable,” “Slightly Capable,” and “Not Capable.” Literal values A, B, C, D, and E will be assigned, respectively.

To answer specific problem number 3, determining the differences between the level kindergarten teacher’s instructional capabilities during COVID-19 pandemic across their profile variables, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized.

To answer specific problem number 4, determining the relationship between the level of kindergarten teacher’s instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic and their profile variables, the Coded Pearson Product correlation coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the details of the analysis and the interpretations of the data concerning the problems posed in the study.

Specifically, it presents the four (4) significant parts of the study through which the data gathered had been discussed. These include the profile variables of the respondents, the level of Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic, the significant differences between the level of Kindergarten teacher's instructional qualifications during the COVID-19 pandemic of the respondents across their profile variables, and the significant relationship between the group of Kindergarten teachers instructional capabilities during COVID 19 pandemic of the respondents and their profile variables.

Profile of the Respondents

Some variables related to the profile of the Kindergarten school teachers in Pozorrubio Districts are considered herein. Such variables included age, sex, civil status, highest educational qualification, number of years teaching kindergarten, and number of relevant training and seminars attended.

In this study, the public Kindergarten school teachers of Pozorrubio Districts of Pangasinan Division II were taken as respondents. They were categorized according to certain variables.

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondents N = 40*

Profile Variables	Variable Category	Frequency	Percentage	
Age	21 - 30	8	20%	
	31 - 40	16	40%	
	41 - 50	15	38%	
	51 - 60	1	2%	
	61 years and above	0	0%	
Sex	Male	2	5%	
	Female	38	95%	
Civil Status	Single	16	15%	
	Married	34	85%	
	Widow/Widower	0	0%	
Highest Educational Qualification	Bachelor Degree Holder	8	20%	
	With M. A. Units	18	45%	
	M.A. Degree Holder	10	25%	
	With PhD/EdD Units	2	5%	
	PhD / EdD Degree Holder	2	5%	
Length of Service Teaching Physical Education and Sports	1 year and below	3	8%	
	2 - 7	22	55%	
	8 - 13	10	25%	
	14 - 19	5	12%	
Number of Trainings/Seminars	International	20 and above	0	0%
		3 and below	40	100%
		4 - 6	0	0%
	National	7 and above	0	0%
		3 and below	25	63%
		4 - 6	10	25%
	Regional	7 and above	5	12%
		3 and below	18	45%
		4 - 6	14	35%
	Division	7 and above	8	20%
		3 and below	4	10%
		4 - 6	14	35%
	7 and above	22	55%	

Age. In terms of age, the majority of the respondent Kindergarten public school teachers belong to the age bracket 31-40 that is 16 or 40 percent, while the rest belong to the age bracket 21-30, 8 or 20 percent, 41-50, 15 or 38 percent, 51 - 60 is 1 or 2 percent and 0 for 61 years old and above. This means that Kindergarten public school teachers are just in their prime age of maturity and capable of effectively delivering instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Sex. The table shows that 38 or 95 percent of females dominate Kindergarten teachers, while 2 or 5 percent are males. This means that the male group of respondents is outnumbered by the female group considering that teaching is a female-dominated profession, as observed in the different public schools in the country.

Civil Status. It can be seen in the table that 34 or 85 percent are married, and 6 or 15 percent are single. This means that the majority of the Kindergarten public school teachers are married.

Highest Educational Attainment. As reflected in the table, 18 or 45 percent earned their M.A. Units, 10 or 25 percent of the respondents have their M.A. Degree, 2 or 5 percent are Ph.D./EdD unit earners, 2 or 5 percent have Ph.D./EdD Degrees, and 8 or 20 percent have a Bachelor Degree. This means that the Kindergarten public school teacher respondents are conscientious about pursuing professional development. They also regard education as a continuous process of learning where they can acquire knowledge and skills, and competencies essential for their professional growth.

Number of Years Teaching Kindergarten. It can be gleaned from the table that the greatest is in the group classification of 2 – 7 years with a frequency of 22 or 55 percent, there is 10 or 25 percent who have 8 - 13 years length of service teaching kindergarten, while 4 or 10 percent have 14 - 19 years and above as Kindergarten teacher and 1 or 2 percent have one year and below teaching kindergarten. It can be said that there is a new breed of Kindergarten teachers in the school's division of Pangasinan. This finding shows that Kindergarten teachers are enjoying their functions/job as Kindergarten teachers with the old ones in the service, thus acquiring some skills. Based on the general knowledge that experience is the best teacher and there are many more things to learn, young Kindergarten teachers in the service are trying their best to attain the goal of having the best Kindergarten teacher in their generation.

It can be seen in the table that most of the Kindergarten public school teachers have attended seven and above relevant training, that is 22 or 55 percent appropriate training in the division level; 8 of the respondents also have seven and above regional training or 20 percent, 5 or 12 percent seven and above national training and seminars and 0 or 0 percent of the respondents had not attended international training and meetings seven and above relevant training. This means that the Kindergarten public school teachers were given enough opportunities to participate in in-service training at different levels except the International training, which nobody attended seven times and above. Seminars, training, and workshops provide excellent avenues for continuing professional education.

Level of Kindergarten Teacher’s Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic

The primary purpose of this study is to determine the level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities during COVID-19 pandemic among Kindergarten teachers in Pozorrubio Districts in the division of Pangasinan II.

A. Preparation of Self-learning Modules

Table 3 presents the level of Kindergarten Teacher’s Instructional Capabilities during COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 3. *Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic Along Preparation of Self-Learning Modules*

Preparation of Self-Learning Modules As a teacher I ...	As assessed by Teachers		As assessed by School Administrators		Combined Rating	
	WM	TR	WM	TR	WM	TR
1. download the self-learning modules from LRMDS.	4.53	HC	4.51	HC	4.52	HC
2. check the self-learning modules are based in MELC.	4.52	HC	4.48	HC	4.50	HC
3. edit the self-learning modules.	4.50	HC	4.46	HC	4.48	C
4. print the learning modules.	4.56	HC	4.54	HC	4.55	HC
5. assort the learning modules.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC
6. photocopy the learning modules.	4.54	C	4.50	HC	4.52	HC
7. ask stakeholders to donate materials for printing self-learning modules.	4.45	C	4.41	C	4.43	C
8. choose learning activities that serve the end goal.	4.41	C	4.39	C	4.40	C
9. prepare activity sheets.	4.54	HC	4.49	C	4.52	HC
10. create performance output activities.	4.46	C	4.40	C	4.43	C
OWM	4.51	HC	4.47	C	4.49	C

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

Table 3 shows that Kindergarten teachers can teach during the COVID-19 pandemic when it comes to preparing self-learning modules for the learners in studying their lessons, as signified in the combined weighted mean in this area of 4.49.

The data in the table also shows that item number 4, “printing the learning modules,” got the highest combined mean of 4.55, described as “Highly Capable” This indicates that teacher respondents are very knowledgeable about printing the self-learning modules for the learners. Item number 8, “Choose learning activities that serve the end goal,” got the lowest combined weighted mean of 4.40 which is described as “Capable” This means that the respondent teachers can not easily decide in choosing which activities they will give their learners to meet the end goal of their lesson.

Table 4 pictures the Kindergarten teacher’s instructional capabilities along distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules.

The table shows the assessment perceived by the teachers and school administrators in the level of Kindergarten teachers’ instructional

capabilities, along distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules. The weighted mean of teachers is 4.54, with a transmuted rating of “Highly Capable.” At the same time, the administrators set the kindergarten teacher’s level of instructional capabilities along distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules with a weighted mean of 4.52, also described as “Highly Capable.”

Table 4. *Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic Along Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules*

<i>Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules As a teacher I...</i>	<i>As assessed by Teachers</i>		<i>As assessed by School Administrators</i>		<i>Combined Rating</i>		
	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	
1. announce scheduled distribution and retrieval of learning modules.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC	
2. orient the parents/guardians about the self-learning modules.	4.54	HC	4.50	HC	4.52	HC	
3. make sure that all printed modules are available to distribute.	4.53	HC	4.51	HC	4.52	HC	
4. emphasize the health protocols to the parents/guardians during distribution and retrieval of learning modules.	4.55	HC	4.53	HC	4.54	HC	
5. release/distribute the self-learning modules on time.	4.55	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC	
6. retrieve the self-learning modules during the scheduled day.	4.53	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
7. provide supplementary materials for modular learning like performance activity sheets.	4.54	HC	4.54	HC	4.54	HC	
8. am well-oriented in delivering and retrieving learning modules.	4.55	HC	4.51	HC	4.53	HC	
9. ask the help of barangay officials in the distribution and retrieval of learning modules.	4.55	HC	4.53	HC	4.54	HC	
10. use the barangay hall for distribution and retrieval of modules.	4.54	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
	OWM	4.54	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

The combined weighted mean is 4.53, described as “Highly Capable.” Five indicators got the highest combined weighted standard, indicator number 1, “announce scheduled distribution and retrieval of learning modules,” indicator 4, “emphasize the health protocols to the parents/guardians during distribution and retrieval of learning modules,” indicator 5, “release/distribute the self-learning modules on time,” indicator 7, “provide supplementary materials for modular learning like performance activity sheets” and indicator 9, “ask the help of barangay officials in the distribution and retrieval of learning modules” got a combined weighted mean of 4.54 with a transmuted rating of “Highly Capable.” The indicator with the lowest combined mean is item number 2 and 3, Item number 2, “Orient the parents/guardians about the self-learning modules,” and item number 3, “Make sure that all printed modules are available to distribute .” combined weighted mean is 4.52 described as “Highly Capable” also.

Table 5. *Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic Along Monitoring of Students Learning*

<i>Monitoring of Students Learning As a teacher I...</i>	<i>As assessed by Teachers</i>		<i>As assessed by School Administrators</i>		<i>Combined Rating</i>		
	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>TR</i>	
1. monitor the learners’ accomplishment of the task provided in the SLMs .	4.54	HC	4.49	C	4.52	HC	
2. monitor the learners progress to inform their future learning goals.	4.52	HC	4.46	C	4.49	C	
3. keep records of activities undertaken.	4.50	HC	4.50	HC	4.50	HC	
4. find ways to communicate with my students to help them understand the lesson.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC	
5. answer their questions thru messenger, text or phone calls.	4.58	HC	4.52	HC	4.55	HC	
6. guide the students in answering the assessment or post-test in the self-learning modules.	4.50	HC	4.48	C	4.49	C	
7. communicate with the students and parents.	4.56	HC	4.53	HC	4.55	HC	
8. always check their performance in learning the content of the modules.	4.55	HC	4.50	HC	4.53	HC	
9. assess them in areas where they find difficult to understand.	4.48	C	4.46	C	4.47	C	
10. give enough time to explain/discuss the lesson.	4.51	HC	4.52	HC	4.52	HC	
	OWM	4.53	HC	4.50	HC	4.52	HC

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

Table 5 shows the level of Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities and student learning monitoring.

The teachers assessed themselves in their instructional capabilities along with monitoring of students learning with a weighted mean of 4.53, described as "Highly Capable." In contrast, the school administrators assessed the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic with a weighted mean of 4.50, also described as "Highly Capable."

The combined weighted mean of this area of the level of instructional capabilities of Kindergarten teachers is 4.52, which is described as "Highly Capable." Indicator number 5 and 7 got the highest combined mean of 4.55 which is described as "Highly Capable," Item 5 is "answer their questions thru messenger, text or phone calls." and item number 7 is "communicate with the students and parents."

There are two indicators that got the lowest combined mean, indicator number 2 and 6, "monitor the learner's progress to inform their future learning goals" and "guide the students in answering the assessment or post-test in the self-learning modules..". Both indicators got a combined mean of 4.49 with a transmuted rating of "Capable."

Table 6 shows the level of Kindergarten instructional capabilities during COVID-19 pandemic, along assessment of learning outcomes.

Table 6. *Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic Along Assessment of Learning Outcomes*

Assessment of Learning Outcomes		As assessed by Teachers		As assessed by School Administrators		Combined Rating	
		WM	TR	WM	TR	WM	TR
<i>The students ...</i>							
1.	check and evaluate students' output from modules' exercises.	4.55	HC	4.53	HC	4.54	HC
2.	require the students to submit reflection videos.	4.56	HC	4.54	HC	4.55	HC
3.	check the portfolio of students work.	4.57	HC	4.53	HC	4.55	HC
4.	use Rubrics in their projects.	4.58	HC	4.56	HC	4.57	HC
5.	interact with students by asking questions to assess their understanding of concepts.	4.55	HC	4.51	HC	4.53	HC
6.	check the assessment test or post test-test of every learning modules.	4.57	HC	4.55	HC	4.56	HC
7.	give and evaluate their assignment.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC
8.	appropriately assess and check their performance output with the use of Rubrics	4.55	HC	4.53	HC	4.54	HC
9.	give paper and pen test in long quiz.	4.56	HC	4.54	HC	4.55	HC
10.	check the summative test of every lesson.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC
OWM		4.56	HC	4.53	HC	4.55	HC

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

The Kindergarten teachers assessed themselves in their instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic along with an assessment of learning outcomes with a weighted mean of 4.56, described as "Highly Capable." In contrast, the school administrators assessed the Kindergarten teacher's level of instructional capabilities and an assessment of learning outcomes with a weighted mean of 4.53, described as "Highly Capable."

The combined weighted mean of the Kindergarten teacher's level of instructional capabilities, along with the learning outcomes assessment, is 4.55, with a transmuted rating of "Highly Capable." The highest weighted mean obtained by indicator 4 is 4.57, described as "Highly Capable." Indicator number 4 is "use Rubrics in their projects. ". The indicator got the lowest mean of 4.53, with a transmuted rating of "Highly Capable" being number 5, "interact with students by asking questions to assess their understanding of concepts."

Regarding the assessment of learning, supporting student learning means focusing on feedback instead of a score or grade. It means helping students to see assessments as learning tools that have an integral role in the learning process rather than as evaluation devices that mark the end of learning. It means making clear to students that the primary purpose of assessments is to verify what they've learned and to identify any learning problems so we can work together to remedy those problems. Hence, cheating on an evaluation serves no purpose other than to delay our efforts to help all students learn well.

Table 7 shows the level of Kindergarten instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic, along with Reporting/Feedback on Students' Outputs and Performances.

It can be seen in the table that the weighted mean given by the Kindergarten teachers in assessing themselves in their instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic is 4.54 with a transmuted rating of "Highly Capable," during the school.

Administrators assessed the Kindergarten teacher's level of instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic with a weighted mean of 4.52, also described as "Highly Capable."

The overall weighted mean of the Kindergarten level of instructional capabilities in this area is 4.53, described as "Highly Capable." Indicator number 3, "make regular time to discuss feedback with the learners or small group basis," got the highest combined weighted

mean of 4.57 which is described as “Highly Capable,” while indicator number 4, “make regular time to discuss feedback with the learners or small group basis” got the lowest combined weighted mean of 4.50 described as “Highly Capable.”

Table 7. *Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic Along with Reporting/ Feedback of Students Outputs and Performance*

Reporting/Feedback of Students Outputs and Performance	As assessed by Teachers		As assessed by School Administrators		Combined Rating		
	WM	TR	WM	TR	WM	TR	
1. address immediately any problems with regard to the distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules.	4.54	HC	4.50	HC	4.52	HC	
2. give opportunity the learners and parents to ask questions about the assessment of their self-learning modules.	4.56	HC	4.52	HC	4.54	HC	
3. make regular time to discuss feedback with the learners or small group basis.	4.58	HC	4.55	HC	4.57	HC	
4. make regular time to discuss feedback with the learners or small group basis.	4.51	HC	4.48	C	4.50	HC	
5. discuss the assessment results to pupils, parents, and other teachers.	4.53	HC	4.51	HC	4.52	HC	
6. listen to the parents'/students' comments and suggestions with regard to the distribution and retrieval of self-learning modules.	4.54	HC	4.54	HC	4.54	HC	
7. recognize students who work well with their self- learning modules and submit their answers on time.	4.53	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
8. give praise and reward to deserving students.	4.56	HC	4.54	HC	4.55	HC	
9. motivate and challenges the learners to further develop their knowledge and skills.	4.54	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
10. focuses on the quality of the learner’s work product and or processes.	4.52	HC	4.50	HC	4.51	HC	
	OWM	4.54	HC	4.52	HU	4.53	HC

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

Summary of the Level of Kindergarten Teacher’s Instructional Capabilities COVID 19 Pandemic

Table 8 provides a general view of the Kindergarten teachers' self-rating and the school administrators' rating in the level of Kindergarten instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 8 shows that the Kindergarten teacher's assessment of their level of instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic had a grand overall weighted mean of 4.53, described as "Highly Capable." This means that Kindergarten teachers are competent in their instruction despite the instructional delivery being far different from the traditional face-to-face classes.

Table 8. *Summary Table of the Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic*

Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic	As assessed by Teachers		As assessed by School Administrators		Combined Rating		
	WM	TR	WM	TR	WM	TR	
1. Preparation of Self-Learning Modules	4.51	HC	4.47	C	4.49	C	
2. Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules	4.54	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
3. Monitoring of Students Learning	4.53	HC	4.50	HC	4.52	HC	
4. Assessment of Learning Outcomes	4.56	HC	4.53	HC	4.55	HC	
5. Reporting/Feedback of Students Outputs and Performance	4.54	HC	4.52	HC	4.53	HC	
	GOWM	4.53	HC	4.50	HC	4.52	HC

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Always/Highly Capable; 3.50 – 4.49 Often/Capable; 2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes/Moderately Capable; 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom/Slightly Capable; 1.00 – 1.49 Never/Not Capable

The school administrators also rated the Kindergarten teachers in their instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic with a grand overall weighted mean of 4.50 with a transmuted rating of “Highly Capable.” This shows that Kindergarten teachers are competent in their instructional delivery, even during the pandemic, using different learning modalities.

The area of this study got the highest combined mean of 4.55, which is described as “Highly Capable” in the assessment of learning outcomes. The preparation of self–learning modules got the lowest combined weighted mean of 4.49, described as “Capable.”

The combined grand overall weighted mean of the level of Kindergarten instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic is 4.52, described as “Highly Capable.”

Differences in the Level of Kindergarten Teacher’s Instructional Capabilities During COVID-19 Pandemic Across their Profile Variables

This section presents the differences in Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic in Pozorrrubio

Districts, Pangasinan Division II.

The table summarizes the computed ANOVA indicated by the F-value for each area covered with its corresponding significance level. This was done to make a more in-depth analysis of data generated in this study whereby the profile of the Kindergarten teachers of Pozorrubio Districts, Division of Pangasinan II, was compared in their level of instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 9 presents the ANOVA showing the significant differences in the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic across their profile variables.

By looking very clearly, at the table, it can be observed that the Kindergarten teachers did not show any significant difference in the level of Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic across their profile variables as indicated by their computed F-value. In other words, the null hypothesis, which states no significant differences in Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic across their profile variables, is accepted at a .05 alpha level of significance as the general point of reference. Such as this case, the level of Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic does not vary when grouped based on the profile variables. Therefore, the profile variables do not influence the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 9. Mean Differences in the Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic and their Profile Variables

Web Based and Non-Web Based Instruction	Preparation of Self-Learning Modules		Distribution and Retrieval of Self-Learning Modules		Monitoring of Students Learning		Assessment of Learning Outcomes		Reporting/ Feedback of Students Outputs and Performance	
	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.	F	Sig.
Age	1.012	.323	.287	.725	.064	.632	.127	.739	.260	.729
Sex	.824	.373	.154	.587	.297	.427	.659	.238	.109	.548
Civil Status	.375	.283	.863	.217	.378	.312	.387	.642	.372	.610
Highest Educational Attainment	.508	.325	.548	.252	.864	.529	.652	.476	.673	.486
Number of Years Teaching Kindergarten	.538	.346	.674	.398	.298	.217	.497	.384	.372	.310
Number of Relevant Trainings Attended										
International	.287	.129	.739	.086	.276	.145	.198	.128	.456	.298
National	.792	.257	.201	.127	.239	.162	.204	.852	.187	.103
Regional	.328	.234	.645	.352	.418	.246	.573	.291	.753	.117
Division	.279	.082	.482	.279	.357	.309	.461	.253	.452	.209

Relationship Between the Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities During COVID 19 Pandemic and their Profile Variables

For further analysis of data gathered in this study, the relationships between the Kindergarten teachers and their profile variables were likewise determined. This was done using the Pearson coefficient of correlation or Pearson r and the t-test for significant correlation. Table 10 shows such relationships.

Table 10 shows the performance of Kindergarten teachers is related to the profile variables in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and relevant training attended at the division level. However, it can be observed from the table that the Pearson r values for relationships between the variables do not reflect any significant relationship at the .05 level along with other profile variables.

Therefore, given such a point of reference, it can be claimed that the null hypothesis stating that there are no significant relationships between the level of Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic and their profile variables is accepted along sex, civil status, and the number of years teaching kindergarten. In other words, the data in the table positively confirm said null hypothesis at the .05 level. This implies that age, highest educational attainment, and relevant training attended at the division level can affect the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic. With this, it can be claimed that at the .05 level of significance, it is 95 percent sure that the age, highest educational attainment, and relevant training attended at the division level are all related to the Kindergarten teacher's instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The data given in the above table can be said with confidence that Kindergarten teachers' instructional capabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic in different areas depend upon age, highest education, and relevant training in the division levels.

Table 10. *Relationship Between the Level of Kindergarten Teachers Instructional Capabilities COVID 19 Pandemic and their Profile Variables*

<i>Profile Variables</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>
Age	.487**	.853
Sex	-.075	.219
Civil Status	.392	.492
Highest Educational Attainment	.368**	.008
Number of Years Teaching Kindergarten	.297	.085
Number of Related Trainings Attended		
Division	.439**	.020
Regional	.295	.271
National	.563	.183
International	.127	.153

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were formulated: The respondent Kindergarten teachers exhibit significant variability in their profiles, with some extreme cases, and are predominantly female. These teachers are performing impressively in their instructional capabilities during the pandemic, with their current performance serving as a foundation for achieving the highest levels of performance. While there are instances where the performance of their instructional capabilities is not significantly comparable, there are also times when it is. The level of instructional capabilities among Kindergarten teachers is influenced by factors such as age, highest educational attainment, and the number of relevant training sessions attended at the division level.

Based on these findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made: Kindergarten teachers should pursue higher educational degrees, such as graduate and doctoral degrees, and engage in professional development through advanced training and seminars. They should strive for excellence in their instructional capabilities by being innovative and resourceful. The Department of Education should allocate additional budget for facilities and equipment needed for modular distance learning. Teachers should develop and implement effective strategies to meet the demands of the new regular education. Collaborative efforts between teachers and parents are essential to monitor learners' progress and provide strategic interventions. Stakeholders should support teachers in addressing challenges as they adapt to new teaching practices. Continuous provision of necessary resources and relevant training for teachers is crucial for delivering quality education. Parents and guardians should be encouraged to support their children's education at home and follow up on assessments and learning performance. Further research should explore more variables to better understand the instructional capabilities of Kindergarten teachers, and additional studies should be conducted to examine these capabilities from different perspectives.

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